

Clinico-Radiologic Profile of Intracranial Space Occupying Lesion Imaged with MRI and Spectroscopy in A Tertiary CenterAswath R. Deepa¹, Bibhu Debbarma², Arun Reang³, Ameena Anju Jaleel⁴¹Post Graduate Trainee, Department of Internal Medicine, Agartala Government Medical College and GB Pant Hospital, Agartala, Tripura, India²Senior Resident, Department of Internal Medicine, Agartala Government Medical College and GB Pant Hospital, Agartala, Tripura, India³Post Graduate Trainee, Department of Radiodiagnosis, Agartala Government Medical College and GB Pant Hospital, Agartala, Tripura, India⁴Junior Resident, Department of Internal Medicine, Lissie Hospital, Kochi, Kerala, India

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Abstract:

Introduction: Magnetic Resonance (MR) spectroscopy is a valuable tool in the differential diagnosis and management of various neurological diseases. MR spectroscopy plays a significant role in differentiating brain tumors from nonneoplastic lesions, obtaining definitive diagnoses, identifying optimal biopsy sites, monitoring treatment responses, and distinguishing treatment-induced changes from recurrent tumors. Its high sensitivity and specificity in differentiating tumors and identifying molecular subtypes of gliomas highlight its diagnostic precision.

Aims and Objective: This study is aimed to investigate the utility of MR spectroscopy (MRS) in differentiating benign and malignant brain tumors compared to conventional MR imaging.

Materials & Method: Thirty patients with suspected brain tumors underwent magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) and proton MRS examinations. MRS techniques included PRESS and multivoxel chemical shift imaging (CSI). This study was performed on Seimens Magnetom Spectra Whole body Scanner.

Results: The present study was a prospective study and done with 30 cases of intracranial SOL over a period of 1 year attending department of General medicine and Radiology of AGMC GBP Hospital. Among the 30 patients, there were 26 males and 4 females. The highest incidence was found in the peak age of 31-40 (23%) and 61- 70 (23%). Among types of Brain Space Occupying Lesions (SOL) Glioma was most common (44%), followed by metastasis (20%). Brain space occupying lesion occurs in intra-axial and extra-axial locations of brain. In present study shows 87% lesions intraaxial and 13% lesions extra-axial.

Conclusion: Magnetic Resonance Spectroscopy provided valuable information about tumor characterization, which can aid in differentiating benign and malignant brain tumors. It's an imaging approach that allows for the non-invasive molecular characterization of a region of interest this information, when used in conjunction with conventional MRI, can improve diagnostic accuracy. Lesions with different underlying causes often appear similar on MRI scans, making MR imaging and MR spectroscopy complementary tools. Together, they provide a comprehensive picture for diagnosing diseases, monitoring their progression, and evaluating treatment responses.

Keywords: Internal Medicine, Radiology.

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Introduction

Magnetic Resonance (MR) spectroscopy is a valuable tool in the differential diagnosis and management of various neurological diseases. This advanced imaging technique provides crucial information about tissue pathophysiology and metabolic profiles, making it indispensable in conditions such as hereditary leukoencephalopathies, demyelinating disorders, multiple sclerosis, infectious brain lesions, neurodegenerative diseases, epilepsy, and acute stroke. MR spectroscopy can reveal metabolic

changes that precede pathological structural changes in brain tissue.[1]MR spectroscopy plays a significant role in differentiating brain tumors from non-neoplastic lesions, obtaining definitive diagnoses, identifying optimal biopsy sites, monitoring treatment responses, and distinguishing treatment-induced changes from recurrent tumors. Its high sensitivity and specificity in differentiating tumors and identifying molecular subtypes of gliomas highlight its diagnostic precision. The male population has a higher risk of primary malignant

brain tumors, whereas the female population has a higher risk of non-malignant tumors.[2]

Magnetic Resonance Spectroscopy (MRS) provides information about the possible extent and nature of changes observed on a routine MRI scan by analysing the presence and ratio of tissue metabolites such as N-acetylaspartate (NAA), creatine, choline, and lactate.[3] These molecules, identifiable by their resonance frequencies, typically include choline (Cho), which reflects membrane turnover; creatine (Cr); and N-acetylaspartate (NAA), a neuronal marker.

While conventional MR imaging excels at revealing anatomical details, it has limitations in pinpointing cellular and molecular changes. MR spectroscopy addresses these limitations by investigating cell density, cell type, and biochemical composition. Lesions with different underlying causes often appear similar on MRI scans, making MR imaging and MR spectroscopy complementary tools. Together, they provide a comprehensive picture for diagnosing diseases, monitoring their progression, and evaluating treatment responses.

Materials and Methods

The present study was a prospective study conducted in a tertiary care center, involving 30 cases of intracranial space-occupying lesions (SOL) over a period of one year. These cases were referred to the Departments of General Medicine and Radiology for MR imaging.

Among the participants, 26 were males and 4 were females. The study utilized an MRI system with a Siemens Magnetom Spectra 3 Tesla. Routine MRI sequences, including T1- and T2-weighted, diffusion, FLAIR, spin echo sequences, and multiplanar imaging, were performed for all patients. Additionally, a contrast study and proton

MRS using single-voxel (PRESS) and multivoxel chemical shift imaging MRS were performed on the 3 Tesla system.

Inclusion Criteria

- Patients of all ages, sexes, and occupations were included.
- Only patients with positive findings of SOL were included.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients with cardiac pacemakers, aneurysm clips, prostheses, or any metallic foreign bodies in situ were excluded.
- Cases where MRI scanning was not possible due to other conditions were excluded.

Techniques Used in MR Spectroscopy:

Four techniques are commonly used in MRS:

- a) STEAM (Stimulated Echo Acquisition Method)
- b) PRESS (Point Resolved Spectroscopy)
- c) ISIS (Image Selected In-vivo Spectroscopy)
- d) CSI (Chemical Shift Imaging)

Results

In the present study, a total of 30 patients with space-occupying lesions (SOL) were diagnosed, of which 26 were male and 4 were female. Brain space-occupying lesions were more common in males (86%) than in females (14%) (Table 1, Figure 1). The highest incidence was found in the age groups of 31-40 years (23%) and 61-70 years (23%) (Table 2, Figure 2). Brain space-occupying lesions occur in both intra-axial and extra-axial locations in the brain. In this study, 87% of the lesions were intra-axial, while 13% were extra-axial (Table 3). Among the types of brain space-occupying lesions, glioma was the most common (44%), followed by metastasis (20%) (Table 4, Figure 3).

Table 1: Distribution of Space Occupying Lesions (SOL) according to sex

Sex	Number	Percentage (%)
Male	26	86
Female	4	14
Total	30	100

Figure 1: Sex Distribution of total 30 patients of SOL

Table 2: Distribution of Space Occupying Lesions (SOL) of Brain according to Age

S.N	Age in years	Number of Patients	Total Percentage (%)
1.	21-30	2	7
2.	31-40	7	23
3.	41-50	5	17
4.	51-60	6	20
5.	61-70	7	23
6.	71-80	3	10
	Total	30	100

Figure 2: Distribution of Space Occupying Lesions (SOL) of Brain according to Age

Table 3: Distribution of Space Occupying Lesions (SOL) according to Location

Location	Number of Patients	Percentage (%)
Extra Axial	4	13
Intra Axial	26	87
Total	30	100

Table 4: Distribution of Space Occupying Lesion (SOL) according to histopathology

Types Of SOL	No. Of Patients	Percentage (%)
Abscess	2	7
Glioma	13	44
Meningioma	4	13
Metastasis	6	20
Tuberculoma	4	13
NCC	1	3
Total	30	100

Figure 3: Distribution of Space Occupying Lesion (SOL) according to histopathology

Discussion

Glioma: Gliomas are the most common type of malignant primary brain tumor and are classified based on their presumed lineage into astrocytomas and oligodendrogliomas. Magnetic resonance spectroscopy (MRS) is one of the most advanced MR techniques, and due to its safe and non-invasive nature, it is primarily used for tumor grading, differentiating between low-grade and high-grade gliomas.

The best indicator of malignancy is the NAA/Cho ratio. Preoperative grading of gliomas can be challenging based on conventional MRI, especially in the absence of significant edema and/or contrast enhancement. This challenge is common even in high-grade tumors. In cases of diagnostic

uncertainty, additional information can be obtained with MRS. Choline levels increase with the degree of malignancy, and the ratios of choline to creatine and choline to N-acetylaspartate are significantly higher in high-grade gliomas compared to low-grade gliomas.[4] Increased choline (Cho) values are related to tumor grade because the presence of necrosis in high-grade tumors is associated with a prominent lipid peak and a reduction in other metabolites.[5]

Higher values of Cho/Cr and Cho/NAA are observed in high-grade gliomas compared to low-grade gliomas. In our study, gliomas were the most common type of brain tumor, accounting for approximately 44%.

Figure 4: Glioma

Meningioma:

Meningiomas are being diagnosed with increasing frequency as more people undergo neuroimaging for various reasons. They are now the most common primary brain tumor, with their incidence increasing with age. Meningiomas are the most common mass lesions of the dura, accounting for 38% of intracranial tumors in women and 20% in men. [6]

They are non-glial neoplasms originating from meningocytes or arachnoid cap cells of the meninges and can be located anywhere the meninges are found. In our study, meningiomas were present in

13% of patients. Meningiomas are more common in females than in males.

On spectroscopy, meningiomas are diagnosed by an increased peak in alanine metabolites, increased peaks in glutamine/glutamate, increased choline (Cho), and decreased peaks of N-acetylaspartate (NAA) and creatine (Cr).

Typically, meningiomas appear as dural-based masses that are iso-intense to grey matter on both T1- and T2-weighted imaging, enhancing homogeneously on MRI. The signal intensity of meningiomas on T2-weighted images correlates with their histological characteristics.

Figure 5: Meningioma

Abscess:

In our study, a total of 2 cases of abscesses were found among the 30 patients, accounting for 7% of the study.

Brain abscesses often occur without systemic signs. Almost half of the patients are afebrile, and the presentation is more consistent with a space-occupying lesion in the brain; 70% of patients present with headaches and/or altered mental status, 50% exhibit focal neurologic signs, and 25% have papilledema.[7] Abscesses can present as single or multiple lesions, resulting from contiguous foci or hematogenous infection, such as endocarditis, or following surgery or trauma.

Interestingly, observations of temporal spectral changes published by Akutsu and associates [8] provide valuable information regarding the response of a studied abscess to surgical or medical treatment. These authors used sequential spectroscopic analysis of brain abscesses to detect changes in metabolite concentrations. Characteristically, they found an absence of acetate, succinate, and cytosolic amino acids after surgical evacuation, while all of these metabolites were present preoperatively.

Spectroscopic analysis can also provide information regarding the exact histological stage of the studied abscess, differentiating between early and late cerebritis, as well as early and late capsular formation.[9]

Metastasis: Out of the 30 patients studied, 6 cases of brain metastasis were observed (20%) in our study population with multiple previously identified primary lesions. Primary cancers such as lung, breast, and melanoma are most likely to metastasize to the brain. Small-cell lung cancer has a particularly high propensity to spread to the brain [10]. On MRI, these lesions were predominantly ill-defined and varied in size. On T1-weighted images, some were isointense, while others were hypointense. However, all lesions were hyperintense on T2-weighted and FLAIR images. MRS revealed lipid peaks in some cases, Cho peaks in others, and a consistent reduction in NAA levels, indicative of neuronal loss in the affected regions.

Neurocysticercosis and Tuberculoma: Both tuberculoma and neurocysticercosis (NCC) can present with seizures and multiple nodular or ring-enhancing lesions in the brain.

MRI in tuberculomas demonstrates conglomerate ring-enhancing lesions located at the grey-white matter junction, predominantly in the frontal and parietal regions. These lesions exhibit a larger extent of perilesional edema. Unlike NCC, they appear as hypo- or isointense lesions with a hypointense rim on T2-weighted images, iso- or hypointense on T1-weighted images, and with no or incomplete suppression on fluid-attenuated recovery (FLAIR) images [11].

In NCC, cranial MRI reveals single or multiple lesions, either cystic with a scolex or in different stages of evolution [12]. These lesions appear as

ring-enhancing lesions with perifocal edema. In our study, NCC was found in 1 patient (3%). The lesion was hypo- to isointense on T1-weighted images and hyperintense on T2-weighted images. MRS showed a choline peak and reduced NAA. Gradient-echo sequences are very useful in detecting calcified lesions. On the other hand, tuberculoma was found in 4 patients (13%) of our study, compared to 10% by Bulabai et al [13].

In MRS, a lactate peak was observed in all cases of tuberculoma. Lactate plays a crucial role in differentiating tuberculoma from other infectious granulomas.

Figure 6: Tuberculoma

Conclusions

Magnetic Resonance (MR) spectroscopy is a valuable tool in the differential diagnosis and management of various neurological diseases. MR spectroscopy plays a significant role in differentiating brain tumors from nonneoplastic lesions, obtaining definitive diagnoses, identifying optimal biopsy sites, monitoring treatment responses, and distinguishing treatment-induced changes from recurrent tumors. Its high sensitivity and specificity in differentiating tumors and identifying molecular subtypes of gliomas highlight its diagnostic precision.

Our study highlights the importance of MR spectroscopy (MRS) in diagnosing various brain tumors. Brain space-occupying lesions were more

common in males (86%) than females (14%). The highest incidence occurred in the age groups of 31-40 years (23%) and 61-70 years (23%). Among the identified lesions, gliomas were the most frequent (44%), followed by metastases (20%). Six cases of brain metastasis (20%) were observed in our study population, with patients having multiple previously identified primary lesions. MRS revealed distinct metabolite patterns: lipid peaks in some cases, choline (Cho) peaks in others, and a consistent decrease in N-acetyl-aspartate (NAA) levels, indicating neuronal loss in the affected regions. Notably, lactate played a crucial role in differentiating tuberculoma from other infectious granulomas. In our study, one patient (3%) had a neurocysticercosis (NCC) diagnosis, and four patients (13%) had tuberculoma. This prevalence of

tuberculoma is slightly higher than the 10% reported by Bulabai et al. importantly; MRS detected a lactate peak in all tuberculoma cases.

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